

TIME AND TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF SURFACE ACCURACY OF HIGH-PRECISION CFRP MIRRORS

J. Koyanagi^{1*}, Y. Arai², S. Utsunomiya³, S. Takeda³, H. Kawada²

¹ Institute of Space and Astronautical Science, JAXA, Sagami-hara, Japan

² Department of Applied Mechanics and Aerospace Engineering, Waseda University, Tokyo Japan

³ Aerospace Research and Development Directorate, JAXA, Tokyo Japan

*Corresponding author (koyanagi.jun@jaxa.jp)

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1 Introduction

One of the main missions of satellite is an observation; there is basically a telescope system inside observing satellites. Mirrors of the telescope system are one of the heaviest parts in the satellites. The maximum weight of the satellite is determined by the launch capacity of the rocket. Of course, the weight of the main mirror is limited but large mirror can facilitate high resolution observation. Hence the materials having both characteristics of high stiffness and light weight are suitable for mirror materials. Carbon fiber reinforced polymeric composite material (CFRP) is superior to not only the specific stiffness also thermal stability [1] so that CFRP can be an attractive alternative material for the satellite mirrors. However, several problems should be solved before applying CFRP to the mirror; one of them is long-term reliability of mirror-surface roughness.

When applying CFRP to mirrors, the surface flatness and accuracy are critical factors. In order to address the problem, the resin coating on the CFRP surface is conventionally implemented, as shown in Fig. 1. We investigated the surface accuracy of the resin-coated CFRP and the sustainability under some harsh situations; we concluded that buff-polishing following the resin coating might be effective to improve surface accuracy [1]. We fabricated four CFRP sandwich mirrors. For two of them, buffing treatment was implemented before the final aluminum deposition. The surfaces of two mirrors were much more accurate and flat than that of remaining mirrors. The sustainability against some harsh environments were also better than that the buffing was not conducted. The previous work resulted also in finding a new problem; a significant groove between fiber tows appear on the surface accuracy measurement and that was presumably

resin rich region. The resin rich region showed reasonable behaviors as follows. When the mirror absorbs moisture, the groove became less significant due to the swelling phenomenon of resin. When the mirror is placed at vacuumed condition for dewater, the groove became more significant due to the dewater shrinkage of resin. As time elapsed, the physical aging shrinkage of the resin made the groove more significant.

In the present study, we report latest results. The surface treatment is removed and resin coating and buff polishing are implemented again, aiming good surface CFRP mirror. We measured the sustainability of the new surface accuracy and temperature dependence of that.

Fig. 1 Resin-coated CFRP surface cross-section [1]

Fig. 2 Grooves appearing on mirror surface [1]

Fig. 3 Fabrication procedure of CFRP sandwich mirror [1]

2 CFRP mirror fabrication [1]

Here, we briefly mention the fabrication process of the CFRP mirror. The prepreg consists of cyanate resin and high modulus continuous carbon fiber. To make the surface flat, an optical flat glass is used as a tool plate. The CFRP plates are fabricated using an auto-clave method. Honeycomb core is inserted between fabricated CFRP plates. The honeycomb core is made of identical materials. After bonding cure, the tool plates are demolded. The Gel-coating is then implemented and buffing is done for a part of mirrors. The mirrors have relatively thin gel-coating layer due to the buffing. Aluminum deposition is finally conducted. Figure 4 is the fabricated CFRP mirrors. The dimensions are 100 x 100 x 30. On the edge, the aluminum deposition is partially done.

Fig. 4 All CFRP sandwich mirrors [1]

3 Measurement

Two mirrors among four of them are selected for the present study (mirror no. 3 and 4 in Table 1). One is that buffing is implemented following aluminum deposition, another is not. For the two mirrors, the surface treatments were removed and gel-coating, buffing and aluminum deposition were implemented again. If the prediction that the buffing is effective to make the surface flatness and accuracy better is correct, it is expected that the retreated surface should be improved even if the previous measurement result of the mirror was bad. Further, since temperature dependence of the surface accuracy is another important factor, we examined that using normal heaters as shown in Fig. 5. The equipment measuring the surface accuracy has to be at constant temperature so that we only heat the mirrors directly as shown in Fig. 5. That results in existence of temperature distribution for the mirror.

Fig. 5 Schematic of measurement system

Hence, we measured temperature distribution by a thermography.

Measured surface roughness and exposure histories of mirrors from fabrication are summarized in Table 1. The results of mirror No. 1 and 2 are previously presented [1]. For No. 1 and 3, buffing following the gel-coating is implemented. For No. 2 and 4, buffing is not implemented. Initially, No. 1 and 3 show good surface roughness, 20nmRMS, on the other hand, No. 2 and 4 show relatively bad roughness. All mirrors are exposed at some various harsh environments such as high temperature, high humidity, vacuumed condition and so on. Every surface deteriorated by the exposures. No. 1 and 3 showed still good surface roughness value compared with No. 2 and 4. After that, we left the mirrors at normal ambient condition for 1 year. It is expected that a shrinkage induced by physical aging progressed sufficiently and saturated during one year. The surface treatments of No. 3 and 4 were then removed. Newly, gel-coating and buffing are implemented for them. After that, a half year elapsed and then we measured the surface roughness by the same way. For No. 3, the surface roughness was 53nmRMS. It remained almost unchanged compared with previous result. However, the surface roughness of No. 4 deteriorated drastically. It was 980nmRMS. As time elapsed, it was assumed the surface condition became bad due to the physical aging and so on. Both results are at ambient room temperature. When the mirrors are heated, the surface roughness of No. 3 was almost kept the same value and that of No. 4 was improved significantly. Measured surface geometries are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig. 7, temperature distributions at the measurements are shown.

Table 1 History from fabrication to measurement

Mirror No.	No. 1	No. 2	No. 3	No. 4
Fabrication	Common	Common	Common	Common
Surface treatment	Gel & Buff	Gel only	Gel & Buff	Gel only
Initial RMS (nm)	20	80	20	100
After harsh exposure	60	180	60	240
Long exposure	-	-	1 year	1 year
Re-treatment	-	-	Gel & Buff	Gel & Buff
After long exposure	-	-	0.5 year	0.5 year
Ambient temperature	-	-	53	980
Elevated temperature	-	-	54	730

(a) No. 3 at room temperature

(b) No. 3 at elevated temperature

(c) No. 4 at room temperature

(d) No. 4 at elevated temperature

Fig 3 Measurement results by Zygo interferometer

(a) Room temperature (b) Elevated temperature

(c) Room temperature (d) Elevated temperature

Fig. 7 Temperature distributions at measurements

At the room temperature the temperature of CFRP mirror is approximately 18°C. The surface roughness was 53nm in RMS for arbitrary 1 inch square. For the elevated temperature, the temperature is 30°C and some distribution as shown in Fig. 3 (b) which occurs due to the method of heating system. The heater point was 35°C and cooler point was 25°C approximately. Even though there is temperature distribution which might affect on the surface roughness, the result remained unchanged. It is to say, the surface roughness of No. 3 is temperature independent. On the other hand, the surface of No. 4 was relatively not accurate. The point here is that when the mirror is heated the surface roughness is improved. When we heat the mirror, resin expands microscopically. That is an opposite phenomenon to the resin shrinkage due to the physical aging, which is expected to progress during exposure. In other words, for the mirror, the temperature elevation is corresponding to getting back of physical aging. For No. 1, the physical aging is considered to progress as well but that does not affect on the surface accuracy. That is the reason that the surface accuracy does not change even at elevated temperature.

Surface geometry deterioration is mainly induced by out-of-plane deformation of the CFRP plates [2].

Microscopically, the fiber alignment is slightly scattering for each prepreg. As a combined effect of the slight fiber misalignment and resin volume change due to swelling and physical aging etc., significant out-of-plane deformation of CFRP plate occurs [2]. The deformation is geometrically saddle type deformation. This is consistent with all the results of Fig. 3. The degree of deformation is dominated by the degree of fiber misalignments. However, since the fiber inherently has torsion on purpose of bundling, eradicating fiber misalignment is essentially difficult. For the meantime, unless we measure the out-of-plane deformation, we cannot predict individual fiber misalignment. It is assumed that No. 3 has consequently no fiber misalignment so that the out-of-plane deformation does not occur if anything happens. However, No. 4 has significant fiber misalignment so that the surface deforms with temperature elevation, physical aging shrinkage etc.

4 Concluding remarks

In the previous work, buffing is considered to be important factor making the surface accuracy better. However, it is found that inherent fiber misalignment is more significantly affects on the surface accuracy than buffing. If the CFRP plate has no fiber misalignment, the plate does not deform with resin deformation; this is ideal. Otherwise, the surface accuracy deteriorates with time and/or temperature. We need to be able to control the fiber misalignment in order to time- and temperature independent accurate CFRP mirror.

References

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